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Intermediate Learner's Opportunities in Modular Modality, their Learning Strategies, and Academic Performance

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Abstract

The study determined the learning opportunities and learning strategies of learners in modular learning among selected intermediate learners and their correlates to their academic performances in Baloi West District, S.Y. 2021-2022. The descriptive-correlational research design was employed and one hundred seventy-six (176) intermediate learners selected through convenience sampling were utilized as participants. Moreover, the study made use of standardized questionnaires validated by the thesis committee of St. Peter's College. The data were treated using frequency and percentage distribution, mean and standard deviation, and Spearman's Correlation. Based on the data gathered, the following findings were drawn: on the learning opportunities in modular modality among learners, the learner's opportunity of having more time to study and bond with their families got the highest mean. In terms of learners' learning strategies in modular modality, they responded sometime. In terms of learners' academic performance, most of the learners had satisfactory performances. On the significant relationship between the academic performance and the learning opportunities in the modular modality of the learners, results depicted that the perceived learning opportunities in the modular modality of the learners were not significantly associated with their academic performance. It was also found that there was no significant association between the learning strategies in modular modality and the learners' academic performance. The study concluded that modular modality provided opportunities for independent learning but the absence of real-time instruction also provided challenges to learners in looking for alternative resources with their limited financial means. An action plan was formulated as remediation to address students' difficulties.

Keywords: *learning opportunities, learning strategies, modular learning, and intermediate learners*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic led several educational institutions to embrace online and modular distance learning. Many pedagogical approaches have changed as a result of all that. It presents difficulties for the educational sectors, with basic education being one of the most severely impacted because of the closure of schools and community learning centers for the physical conduct of lessons.

With the closure of schools, the challenges to continue learning to grow as continued school closure could lead to education stagnation. When there is education stagnation, the development of human skills and resources could be put at risk. This situation could adversely affect the economic condition of the country. It was tangibly observed at those times of pandemic, many people were worried about how hard the education of their children would be affected. The challenges met by the people were beyond ordinary as they were coupled with fear and apprehension.

Even in the most challenging times, the Department of Education (DepEd) is dedicated to fulfilling its responsibility to make education accessible and successful. On the basis of the Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), it had actively prepared its activities. Flexible learning delivery methods had been implemented for the school year 2020–2021, since it was required from the Central Office down to the school level, in order to continue providing instruction to students despite the pandemic situation (DepEd Order 12, s. 2020).

In accordance with the needs of the students and community health constraints, DepEd migrated real-time learning to alternative learning modalities as part of the learning continuity strategy. These learning methods combined in-person or in-module delivery of learning materials to the participants' homes with online distant learning. In locations without access to computers or the internet, radio-based and modular learning materials were also used (Llego, 2020).

However, because of a lack of infrastructure and technology to accommodate online learning, several regions solely used the printed modular learning option. Learning modules were printed and weekly home learning plans (WHLP) were generated from the individual learning plan (ILP) made by teachers to suit the aforesaid learning modality. The employment of the printed learning modality then affords a way for the teachers to deliver the printed learning to the students who did not have access at home (Dangle & Sumaong, 2020).

It was believed that learners must make a variety of modifications and accept these new developments in their learning. As a result, they could exhibit particular traits and behaviors during learning. Independent study was encouraged through the use of self-learning resources. The development of improved self-study or learning abilities had been cited one of the advantages of adopting self-learning activities and instructional resources for training. By completing the activities outlined in the module, they got a sense of responsibility. The students could advance on their own with little to no help from others. They were empowered and learned how to learn. They

exhibited various learning methods as a result (Bonifacio, 2020).

Learning methods are often the main emphasis of definitions of learning techniques. Learning methods, according to Aragon (2011), are a person's preferred method of obtaining, arranging, and processing information. It is seen as the actions pertaining to emotive, cognitive, and psychological engagement with learning settings. Along with motivation and information-processing habits, it also includes the preferred methods that students use to obtain, process, and retain information during teaching (Sheik, 2012).

The examination of learners' possibilities and learning methodologies made by online education in the nation was deemed necessary by the researcher. Because of the lack of face-to-face instruction brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic, the Department of Education established flexible learning options for pupils. In light of the epidemic among a chosen group of public primary students in the Baloi West District, the current study sought to add to the increasing body of research on learners' possibilities and learning preferences. The study's findings were anticipated to make a substantial contribution to the nation's educational sectors in strengthening their learning continuity programs.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the learning opportunities and learning strategies of learners in modular learning among selected intermediate learners and their correlates to their academic performances during the third (3rd) quarter of the S.Y. 2021-2022 in Baloi West District. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the learning opportunities for intermediate learners in the modular modality in terms of:
 - 1.1. independent learning,
 - 1.2. access to learning materials, and
 - 1.3. reduced costs for learning?
2. What are the learning strategies of intermediate learners in modular modality?
3. What is the academic performance of the learners during the third quarter of S.Y. 2021-2022?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of learners and their learning opportunities in modular modality?
5. Is there a significant relationship between learners' academic performance and their learning strategies in modular modality?
6. What action plan can be designed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

A descriptive-correlational research design was employed in this study for it described the variables and the relationship that occurs naturally between and among the presented variables. This was a descriptive study since it tried to test the opportunities for intermediate learners in modular modality and their learning strategies. This was also a correlational design since the study tried to determine the relationship among the academic performance of learners, their opportunities in modular modality, and their learning strategies.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were one hundred seventy-six (176) learners from one-hundred-fifty respondents came from Baloi Central Elementary School and fifty (50) were from Pacalundo Integrated School, Division of Lanao del Norte. They were all intermediate learners from grade 7 to 10 in the aforementioned schools in the School Year 2021-2022. They were selected based on their availability and willingness to participate in the study.

Convenience was used in the study because the respondents were picked at the convenience of both the researcher and the participants, and the number of participants or respondents was based on the permissible number in the subject of research. In this study, convenience was employed to allow researchers to collect data that would not have been feasible otherwise. This was made possible due to the onslaught of the pandemic. According to Abbas (2018), a 10% rule might be used to determine the number of responses. Considering there were around 1763 students in both institutions, 176 of them were taken.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Schools</i>	<i>Total Actual Sample</i>	<i>Target Respondents</i>
Baloi Central Elementary School	1443	126
Pacalundo Integrated School	320	50
Total	1763	176

Instrument

The instrument that was utilized in this study was that of Alcala (2021) entitled "Modular distance learning modality: Challenges of teachers in teaching amid the Covid-19 Pandemic". There was no modification in the questionnaire; however their Maranao translations were provided to fit the setting of the study, such translation was done by a secondary master teacher who was a content evaluator of Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM).

The questionnaire was divided in three (3) parts. Part I included information as to the respondent's profile with respect to ages, sex, and their third quarter general average in the current school year. Part II was about the learner's perceived opportunities in modular learning. Part III included items that asked on learners' strategies in modular learning. The foregoing questionnaire was no longer pilot tested since all the questions were adapted as they were used in the study of Alcala (2021).

Procedure

The researcher visited the two (2) selected schools covered in the study. To expedite the data gathering, permission to conduct the study was obtained from the school's division superintendent, principals, and teachers. All communications were signed and approved by the concerned authorities.

During the distribution of the questionnaire, the researcher explained to the parents the importance and mechanics on how to answer some parts of it. The respondents were given one week to return the survey questionnaires. Confidentiality of their answers was assured by the researcher on the respondents.

To gather data on the respondents' perception of opportunities in modular learning modality, the researcher asked them to rate assigned perception on the scale of five (5) for always, four (4) for often, three (3) for sometimes, two (2) for rarely, and one (1) for never. Moreover, in processing the data on learners' strategies in modular learning modality, the respondents were asked to respond by placing check (✓) in the given indicators using the 4 Likert scales.

After obtaining the responses of the respondents, the researcher tabulated the responses through a spreadsheet to undergo statistical treatment.

Data Analysis

The following statistical techniques were employed to answer the different problems presented. Mean and Standard Deviation, Frequency Count and Percentage, and Spearman r correlation.

Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation were used to describe the opportunities of learners in modular modalities and their learning strategies, moreover, frequency and Percentage were utilized to determine the academic performance of learners based on DepEd Standards.

Frequency and Percentage were used to describe the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and their third (3rd) quarter-final grades.

Spearman r Correlation was employed to measure the strength and direction of association between two ranked variables. This tool was deemed appropriate to use here because the variable were rank-ordered as there were highest and lowest values.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered by the researcher as well as the analysis and interpretation.

Problem 1: What are the learning opportunities of the intermediate learners in the modular modality in terms of independent learning, access to learning materials, and reduced costs for learning?

Table 2. *Learning Opportunities in Modular Modality of the Learners in Terms of Independent Learning*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
IL1. Modular modality provides me sufficient time to study and more time to bond with my family.	4.25±0.56	Often
IL2. Modular modality helps me discover my abilities.	4.00±0.40	Often
IL3. I have more time to answer my modules alone.	4.13±0.56	Often
IL4. Modular modality allows me to manage my own study timetable.	3.82±0.44	Often
IL5. I became more independent in looking for solutions to comply with my school requirements.	4.19±0.53	Often
Total Measure	4.08±0.24	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never, 1.50-2.49 Rarely, 2.50-3.49 Sometimes, 3.50-4.49 Often, 4.50-5.00 Always, SD - Standard Deviation

Table 2 presents the learning opportunities of the learners in modular modality in terms of independent learning. The result revealed that the respondents often perceived these opportunities with most of them affirming that these opportunities often provided them with sufficient time to study and more time to bond with their respective families and with the lowest few of them often affirming that with the modular modality, they discovered their abilities. This result showed that most of the intermediate learners got ample time to study and at the same time gained opportunities to become closer to their families while a few of them had discovered their abilities.

The preceding information meant that most of the intermediated learners in the research locale had developed independent learning. According to Tren (2020), the learners who had ample time to study and who felt cared for by their family, as well they realized that they had abilities tended to develop the ability to learn independently.

It could be analyzed that despite the challenges in students' learning brought by the pandemic, modular modality allowed learners to become more independent. This implied that modular distance learning allowed learners to have control of their own learning and progress.

Tria (2020) observed that some learners under the modular learning modality did not have the chance and privilege to have access to the internet. Economic barriers and poor internet connection were two of the main causes. Some learners learned to do self-study which was one of the many advantages of distance learning. And through self-study, they could keep track of their own learning and become even more interested in learning.

According to Gonzales (2015), modular modality was among the teaching approaches that allow students to learn alone, independently, and without assistance at their own pace. He asserted that this learning approach varied from the conventional teaching methods wherein the students just listened to learn the concepts presented by the teachers all throughout classroom sessions. In this modality, students explored their own abilities independently.

Table 3. Learning Opportunities in Modular Modality of the Learners in Terms of Access to Learning Materials

Indicators	Mean \pm SD	Description
ALM1. I am provided with free self-learning modules.	4.89 \pm 0.31	Always
ALM2. I can access learning materials at home through a laptop or a computer.	2.93 \pm 0.57	Sometimes
ALM3. I can freely watch DepEd TV at home to aid me in my modules.	2.35 \pm 0.52	Rarely
ALM4. I can easily contact my teachers through their provided information on the modules when I am experiencing difficulty in answering my modules.	3.32 \pm 0.57	Sometimes
ALM5. I can access at home whatever resources are available for me.	4.13 \pm 0.54	Often
Total Measure	3.52 \pm 0.25	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never, 1.50-2.49 Rarely, 2.50-3.49 Sometimes, 3.50-4.49 Often, 4.50-5.00 Always, SD - Standard Deviation

Table 3 presents the learning opportunities in modular modality of the learners in terms of access to learning materials. Result described that the learners were always provided with free self-learning modules (M=4.89, SD=0.31) while the lowest mean entailed that "I can freely watch DepEd TV at home to aid me in my modules" (M=2.35, SD=0.52). They responded that they could often access at home whatever resources available to them (M=4.13, SD=0.54) but sometimes they could easily contact their teachers through their provided information on the modules when they experienced difficulty in answering their modules (M=3.32, SD=0.57). The learners could rarely watch DepEd TV at home to aid them in their modules (M=2.35, SD=0.52).

It could be analyzed that learners had the privilege to access learning materials at home through the provided electronic copies of self-learning modules and activities. The Department of Education also initiated free access to live classes on Facebook and YouTube through their DepEd TV-partnered channels and livestreams. However, not all learners had access to these platforms. Apparently, modular modality was viewed to be efficient in giving free learning materials to learners.

In the study of Llego (2020), he mentioned that not all students and families had access to the internet. They were prepared enough to buy gadgets and laptops for their children. As a result, some learners relied only on learning materials available for them. It was a sad reality for some households but the government could not afford to supply gadgets for every learner.

Consequently, Fernandez et al. (2020) also mentioned that poor learners face significant problems in distance learning because they were deprived of the benefits of technology. Unlike privileged learners, they struggled in communicating to their teachers digitally. Also, they were also unable to look for alternative sources of information.

Table 4. Learning Opportunities in Modular Modality of the Learners in Terms of Reduced Costs for Learning

Indicators	Mean \pm SD	Description
RCL1. I do not need to spend on transportation every day because of modular learning arrangements.	4.28 \pm 0.45	Often
RCL2. I do not need to buy learning materials because the provided modules are free.	4.16 \pm 0.47	Often
RCL3. I experienced financial freedom because of fewer school requirements.	3.14 \pm 0.59	Sometimes
RCL4. Modular learning modality makes me unbothered by financial constraints especially for fares and daily allowances.	4.12 \pm 0.62	Often
RCL5. Modular distance learning gives me direct access to learning materials without actually being at school.	4.37 \pm 0.58	Often
Total Measure	4.01 \pm 0.26	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never, 1.50-2.49 Rarely, 2.50-3.49 Sometimes, 3.50-4.49 Often, 4.50-5.00 Always, SD - Standard Deviation

Table 4 presents the learning opportunities in modular modality of the learners in terms of reduced costs for learning. Result showed that they oftentimes believed that modular distance learning gave them direct access to learning materials without actually being at school (M=4.37, SD=0.58) while the lowest mean entailed that they sometimes experienced financial freedom because of fewer school requirements (M=3.14, SD=0.59).

It can be analyzed that the modular modality implemented was financially easy for learners. Even without the aid of instructional

materials, they were provided with opportunities to access free learning materials without spending a centavo.

According to Gonzalez (2015), distance learning modalities lessen the expenses of some learners who cannot afford the time and finances required for a distance learning setup. Teachers also saved up their efforts in going to school every day. However, their tasks were to keep learners' engagement remain constant. Some surveys among teachers revealed that there was an estimated forty-three percent of students who were disengaged during distance learning. Most of them did not have access to the internet at home.

Table 5. *Consolidated Findings of the Learning Opportunities in Modular Modality of the Learners*

<i>Learning Opportunities</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Independent Learning	4.08±0.24	Often
Access to Learning Materials	3.52±0.25	Often
Reduced Costs for Learning	4.01±0.26	Often
Total Measure	3.87±0.16	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never, 1.50-2.49 Rarely, 2.50-3.49 Sometimes, 3.50-4.49 Often, 4.50-5.00 Always, SD - Standard Deviation

Table 5 shows the consolidated findings of the learning opportunities in the modular modality of the learners. As depicted in the result, the learner's opportunity of being independent in their learning (M=4.08, SD=0.24), followed by reduced costs for learning and lastly access to learning materials. They highly believed that in the modular modality of learning they became more independent learners.

The results implied that modular distance learning provided independent learning to learners. Students controlled their own learning and they do self-study. According to Correos (2020), self-study was a method of learning that identified students having directed their own study pace outside the classroom without supervision and assistance. It could also be a very valuable way for some students because they were able to take control of what and how they were learning.

Problem 2: What are the learning strategies of intermediate learners in modular modality?

Table 6. *Learning Strategies of Intermediate Learners in Modular Modality*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
LS1. I plan what I am going to do every day.	4.28±0.45	Often
LS2. Participate in computer-mediated discussions and collaborative learning activities conducted synchronically online for learners.	2.32±0.47	Rarely
LS3. Submit my assignments on time through the given length of time to complete the given tasks.	4.10±0.56	Often
LS4. Ability to adopt innovative practices in learning.	3.05±0.64	Sometimes
LS5. Engage in the independent discovery of available resources online.	3.32±0.49	Sometimes
LS6. I do group study with my classmates.	3.16±0.60	Sometimes
LS7. I make my own study timeline.	4.18±0.39	Often
LS8. I look for available learning materials through the DepEd website.	2.99±0.44	Sometimes
LS9. I borrow books from my neighbors.	2.95±0.48	Sometimes
LS10. When I have extra time, I watch DepEd TV to learn more.	4.36±0.48	Often
Total Measure	3.47±0.20	Sometimes

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never, 1.50-2.49 Rarely, 2.50-3.49 Sometimes, 3.50-4.49 Often, 4.50-5.00 Always, SD - Standard Deviation

Table 6 presents the learning strategies of intermediate learners in modular modality. The result displayed that the highest mean showed learners oftentimes watched DepED TV and learned more when they had extra time (M=4.36, SD=0.48), while the lowest mean displayed that they rarely participated in computer-mediated discussions and collaborative learning activities conducted synchronically online for learners (M=2.32, SD=0.47).

It could be analyzed that learners amid the modular modality became more extra independent and planners of their own learning. Responsible learners worked one at a time to ensure that all of their modules were taken care of. Some learners were also observed by some teachers to become more resourceful in looking for alternative resources at home.

Planning instruction around students' readiness, interests, and learning preferences empowered them to drive their own learning. According to Tasnim et al. (2021), planning to learn influenced the academic performances of learners because planning got them to speed up everything that they needed to do. The learning materials might be new or complex, but they could achieve more work if they planned what to do first.

Further, not all learners participated in computer-mediated instructions or could use social media platforms amid the pandemic to use as a learning strategy because of financial constraints. Learners' geographical location also influenced their engagement to use social media platforms more often (Acala et al., 2021).

Problem 3: What is the academic performance of learners?

Table 7 presents the academic performance of the learners as based on their recent grades. As observed, 71 or 71% of the total learners had satisfactory performance, 16 or 16% of them belonged to very satisfactory performance, 10 or 10% of them had an outstanding

performance, and 3 or 3% of them belonged to fair performance.

Table 7. *Academic Performance of Learners*

<i>Academic Performance</i>		<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Outstanding(O)	90-100	10	10.0
Very Satisfactory(VS)	85-89	16	16.0
Satisfactory(S)	80-84	71	71.0
Fair(F)	75-79	3	3.0
Total		100	100.0

The results were indications that the use of modules was effective for some of them. Apparently, there were 3 or 3% of them who had fair performance which implied that they were having difficulties with the modular modality.

There were several reasons that influenced students' academic success in a blended learning classrooms such as difficult subject matter, complex learning materials, and personal problems at home. Students' attitudes toward learning were also found as other reasons such as not performing their home works and lack of motivation. Other reasons were also on the personal aspect such having test anxieties and concentration problems (Lapada et al., 2020).

According to Ambayon (2020), the pandemic lockdowns also influenced learners' academic performances. Although, virtual education provided an opportunity for independent learning, learners suffered from challenges of unavailability of practical reasons such as basic subjects like Mathematics and Science.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of learners and their learning opportunities in modular modality?

Table 8. *Relationship between the Academic Performance and the Learning Opportunities in Modular Modality of the Learners*

<i>Learning Opportunities</i>	<i>Academic Performance</i>		<i>Remarks</i>
	<i>Spearman r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
Independent Learning	0.037ns	0.715	No significant relationship
Access to Learning Materials	0.034ns	0.737	No significant relationship
Reduced Costs for Learning	0.046ns	0.649	No significant relationship
Total Measure	0.048ns	0.634	No significant relationship

Note: Analysis is based on Spearman-rank Correlation ns-not significant at 0.05 level (P-value > 0.05)

Table 8 presents the relationship between the learning opportunities and academic performance of the intermediate learners in modular modality. The results depicted that there was no significant relationship between the learning opportunities and the learners' academic performance in modular modality. The learning opportunity aspects, independent learning access to learning materials, and reduced costs for learning were not significantly related to the learners' academic performance as their p-values (0.715, 0.737, and 0.649 respectively) were greater than the r-values (0.037, 0.034, and 0.046 respectively).

This result suggested that the learners' academic performance was not influenced by their learning opportunities in modular modality. Independent learning, access to learning materials, and reduced costs for learning could not explain or predict the learners' academic performance. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the academic performance and the learning opportunities in modular modality of the learners was not rejected.

The flexible learning options mandated by the Department of Education helped learners become independent learners and the way their teachers handled the delivery of information could affect their attitudes and behaviors in learning.

According to Olamo et al. (2019), learners' academic performance was found also to be influenced by other factors. Some learners were cognitively gifted. Regardless of the situation in learning, they could still ace to get good performances if they were highly motivated and satisfied with their learning. Meanwhile, Tasnim et al. (2021) added that students' academic performance was affected by several factors which included students' learning skills, parental background, peer influence, teachers' quality, and learning infrastructure among others.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of learners and their learning strategies in modular modality?

Table 9 presents the relationship between the academic performance and the learning strategies in modular modality of the learners using the Spearman-rank Correlation statistic. Data analysis showed that there was no significant association between the learning strategies in modular modality and the academic performance of the learners ($r=0.038 < p=0.707$).

This result could be inferred that the academic performance of the learners was independent to their perceived learning strategies in modular modality and that these strategies could not predict their academic performance. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the academic performance and the learning strategies in modular modality of the learners was not rejected.

Table 9. Relationship Between the Academic Performance and Their Learning Strategies in Modular Modality

Variable	Academic Performance		Remarks
	Spearman r-value	p-value	
Learning Strategies in Modular Modality	0.038ns	0.707	No significant relationship

Note: Analysis is based on Spearman-rank Correlation ns-not significant at 0.05 level (P-value > 0.05)

Overall academic performance was not influenced by learning style. Academic performance in different forms of assessment was not influenced by learning style. Students with high pragmatist scores did not perform better in modules with a large practical component such as topographical anatomy (Wilkinson et al., 2014). In addition, according to the findings, regular study, hard work, dedication and self-Confidence, regular attendance, support by family members and other had a high impact on the academic performance of undergraduate students. On the other hand, the noisy and unfriendly environment in the institution, insufficient effort in studying, and lack of interest in the subject impacted negatively.

Conclusions

Despite the modular approach, the learners were given both opportunities and obstacles. In addition to their financial difficulties, they had trouble accessing supplementary learning resources to back up their answers on the courses. They were given the opportunity to learn independently and save money on transportation and allowances. However, they also battled with the additional costs associated with purchasing their own technology and internet data connections as needed. As a result, the modular learning approach offered options for independent learning, but the lack of real-time instruction also made it difficult for students to find alternate resources given their limited financial resources.

Further, the academic performance of the learners was independent to their perceived independent learning, access to learning materials, reduced costs for learning, and learning strategies. The result concluded that the learners' academic performance was not influenced by their learning opportunities and learning strategies in modular modality.

Based on the Competence Motivation Theory, people who were successful when attempting new skills or tasks and received positive reinforcement will internalize a self-reward system as well as a set of mastery goals. This could have a positive and long-term effect on their confidence. It could also help them recognize that they could control their performance. High perceptions of competence and control created feelings of pleasure that maintained or led to an increase in competence motivation as cited by Fernandez (2020).

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were drawn.

Learners should be provided with remediation programs regularly to address their difficulties and challenges in learning.

Teachers should design their strategic plans on how they could provide skills for learners in planning their own tasks which is appropriate in times like these and in the course of distance learning.

School administrators must find ways to involve parents through communication, consultation before decision-making family opportunities at school, and support for home-based learning.

Future researchers should continue to expand more on the current research about modular modality to help the education sector in the country to secure preparedness for future challenges on the education systems.

References

- Abbas, J. (2018). How many respondents are required in conducting a research paper? ResearchGate.researchgate.net.
- Alcala, M. & Castroverde, F. (2021). Modular distance learning modality: Challenges of teachers in teaching amid the Covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 2021 Volume 10 Number 8, 7-15.
- Ambayon, E. (2020). Modular-based approach and student's achievement in literature. *International Journal of Education and Literary Studies*, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.8n.3p.32>.
- Aragon, L. (2011). Language learning strategies of students at different levels of speaking proficiency. *Education Quarterly*, 68(1), 16-35.
- Bagood, J. B. (2020). Teaching-learning modality under the new normal. Philippine Information Agency. <https://pia.gov.ph/features/articles/1055584>.
- Bernardo, J. (2020, July 30). Modular learning most preferred by parents: DepEd. ABS-CBN news. <https://news.abs-cbn.com/news/07/30/20/modular-learning-most-preferred-by-parentsdepd>.
- Bonifacio, E. (2020). Distance learning situations in times of covid-19. *Journal of research on technology in education*, 7(3), 09-26, 2020.
- Correos, J. (2020). Techniques for assessing students' e-learning achievement. *International Journal of the Computer, the Internet and*

Management, 12(2), 26-31

Dangle, Y. & Sumaong, J. (2020). The implementation of modular distance learning in the Philippine secondary public schools. 3RD International Conference on Advanced Research in Teaching Education.

DepEd Order No. 12, s.2020. Adoption of the basic education learning continuity plan for school year 2020-2021 in light of the COVID-19 public health emergency. Department of Education, June 06, 2020.

Duyan, V. (2020). Effectiveness of modular approach in teaching and learning on the chemistry of gases and their applications at University of Perpetual Help System Laguna (UPHSL). International Journal of Education Research. Vol. 5 No. 1 p 59-69.

Estrada, P. (2021). Effect of modular distance learning approach to academic. International Journal of Research Studies in Education, 2021 Volume 12, 9-15.

Fernandez, G. (2020) Effect of m-learning on students' academic performance mediated by facilitation discourse and flexibility. Knowledge Management & E-Learning, Vol.11, No.2.

French, S. (2015). The benefits and challenges of modular higher education curricula. Issues and Ideas Paper of the University of Melbourne.

Ghoneem, K., & Alelaimat, A. (2012). The effect of educational modules strategy on the direct and postponed study's achievement of seventh primary grade students in Science in comparison with the conventional approach. Higher Education Studies Vol. 2, No. 2; June 2012.

Giffords, F. (2009). Implementing integrated performance assessment. Alexandria, VA: American Council on the Teaching of Foreign Languages (ACTFL).

Gonzalez, H.E. (2015) Distance Education and the Evolution of Online Learning in The United States. University of Denver, Digital Commons DU.https://digitalcommons.du.edu/law_facpub/24.

Gossenheimer, R., Taws,D., & Wheller, Y. (2016). Impact of distance education on academic performance. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0175117>.

Hubert, M., & Sanchez, K. (2015). Distance learning approach and student's achievement in literature. International Journal of Education and Literary Studies, 8(3).

Ibyatova, I., Oparina, K., & Rakova, E. (2018). A modular approach to teaching and learning English grammar in technical universities. Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference 1:139.

Lapada, A. A., Miguel, F.F., Robledo, D. A. R., & Alam, Z. F. (2020). Teachers' covid-19 awareness, distance learning education experiences and perceptions towards institutional readiness and challenges. International Journal of Learning, Teaching, and Educational Research, 19(6).

Nardo, K. (2017). Student outcomes and perceptions of instructors' demands and support in online and traditional classrooms. Internet and Higher Education, 9(4), 257-266.

Llego, MA. (2020). DepEd learning delivery modalities for school year 2020-2021. TeacherPh. <https://www.teacherph.com/deped-learning-delivery-modalities>.

Maldonado, C., River, F., Iglesias, A., & Moreno, C. (2020). Characterization of resilient adolescents in the context of parental unemployment. DOI: 10.1007/s12187-019-09640-8

Manlangit, A., Paglumotan, C., & Sapera, P. (2012). Are the functions of teachers in e-learning and face-to-face learning environments really different? Educational Technology & Society. 12(4), 331-343.

Mercurio, K. (2020). Global perspectives on blended learning: Insight from WebCT and our customers in higher education. In C. J. Bonk, & C. R. Graham (Eds.), Handbook of blended learning: Global perspectives, local designs, (pp. 155–168).

Moore, M., & Thompson, M. (1990). The effects of distance learning: A summary of literature. ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED330 321.

Moorhouse, B. L. (2020). Adaptations to a face-to-face initial teacher education course 'forced' online due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Journal of Education for Teaching, pp. 1-3.

Musingafi, R., Paterson, H., & Wack, D. (2015). Challenges for open and distance learning (odl) students: Experiences from students of the Zimbabwe open university. Journal of Education and Practice. Vol.6, No.18, 2015.

Olamo,T., Mengistu, Y., & Dory, F. (2019). Challenges hindering the effective implementation of the harmonized modular curriculum: The case of three public Universities in Ethiopia. Scientific Research Publishing. Creative Education, 2019, 10, 1365-1382.

- Padmapriya, P.V. (2015). Effectiveness of self-learning modules on achievement in biology among secondary school students. *International Journal of Education and Psychological Research (IJEPR)*. Volume 4, Issue 2, June 2015.
- Pashler, H., McDaniel, M., Rohrer, D., & Bjork, R. (2009). Learning styles: Concepts and evidence. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 9, 10.
- Pellegrino, J. (2011). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55(1), 68-78.
- Quinones, R. (2020). DepEd learning delivery modalities for school year 2020- 2021. *Journal of Education and Practice*, (8), 2021.
- Sejpal, K. (2013). Performance-based assessment: Implications of task specificity. *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, 13(1), 5-8.
- Sheik, K. (2012). Assessment beliefs and practices of language teachers in primary education. *International Journal of Instruction*, 6(1), 102-118.
- Shuja, A., Ternes, C., & Wesson, T. (2019). Effect of m-learning on students' academic performance mediated by facilitation discourse and flexibility. *Knowledge Management & E-Learning*, Vol.11, No.2. Jun 2019.
- Smart, L. & Cappel, S. (2016). A survey of national Taiyuan senior-high-school students' interest in learning music and demand for self-decision. MA, Taiwan: Department of Music, National Taiwan Normal University.
- Tria, M. (2020). M-learning in education: Omani undergraduate students' perspective. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 176, 834-839.
- Uson, L. (2012). Setting the standards in teaching performance. *International Journal of Academic Research*.
- Vergara, M. (2011). The relationship of self-efficacy, motivation, and critical thinking disposition to achievement and attitudes when an illustrated web lecture is used in an online learning environment. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 46(2), 12-23.
- Zhang, W., Wang, Y., Yang, L., & Wang, C., (2020). Suspending classes without stopping learning: China's education emergency management policy in the covid-19 outbreak. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, vol. 13, np. 55, pp. 1-6.

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